

Combating Environmental Pollution Combining Clean-Up by Bioremediation and Pyrolysis

Sai Rithika N, Niveetha V, Praveena S, Swetha D, Aadil Ahmed Irshath and
Anand Prem Rajan*

*School of Bio Sciences and Technology (SBST)
Vellore Institute of Technology (VIT), Vellore – 632 014, Tamil Nadu, INDIA*

**Corresponding author: Dr Anand Prem Rajan
Professor*

*School of Bio Sciences and Technology (SBST)
Vellore Institute of Technology (VIT),
VELLORE, Tamil Nadu, India*

Date of Submission: 09-05-2023

Date of Acceptance: 20-05-2023

ABSTRACT: Heavy metal soil contamination has grown widespread due to increased geologic and human activity. These soils result in decreased plant growth, performance, and production. Heavy metals, organic pollutants, and toxic refuse have all negatively impacted the natural environment to the disadvantage of people. Both anthropogenic and natural catastrophes like storms and volcanic events produce these pollutants. Food security could be seriously jeopardized if toxic metals build up in farming grounds and enter the food chain. Heavy metal-polluted soil can be effectively treated by bioremediation. It is a well-known technique that is primarily performed in situ, making it appropriate for the establishment of crops on treated soils. Therefore, by utilizing the innate biological processes of microorganisms and plants to get rid of dangerous contaminants, bioremediation is an effective and environmentally responsible way to clean up habitats that have been contaminated with heavy metals. Different processes are used by plants and microorganisms for the bioremediation of contaminated soils. In the bioremediation of heavy metal - contaminated soils, using plants to remediate polluted soils is an increasingly popular method. A strategy to bioremediation that enables a more effective cleanup of heavy metal-polluted soils combines both microorganisms and plants. The term "pyrolysis" refers to the chemical breakdown of organic compounds brought about by heat in the absence of oxygen. By using contaminated biomass phytoremediation, the adsorption-pyrolysis technique to reclaim metals from solution can be made feasible. The technology can achieve three

goals: the removal of phytoremediation generated metals-contaminated biomass, the absorption of metals, and the recycling of metals-contaminated biomass.

KEYWORDS: Bioremediation, heavy metals, pyrolysis, soil contamination, pollution, phytoremediation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Even though heavy metals are naturally present in soil, human and geological processes have increased their concentration to levels that are detrimental to both plants and animals. Among them are the mining and smelting of metals, the burning of fossil fuels, the use of pesticides and fertilizers in agriculture, the manufacturing of batteries and other metal products in the industrial sector, the disposal of sewage sludge, and the use of fertilizers and pesticides in agriculture [1].

It has been shown that plants growing in soils contaminated with heavy metals experience a loss in growth because of alterations in physiological and biochemical processes. Plant growth continues to fall, which lowers production and eventually causes food insecurity. Soil cleanup for heavy metal contamination cannot be overstated.

There are several techniques for cleaning up metal-polluted soils, ranging from physical and chemical techniques to biological techniques. Most physical and chemical techniques (such as soil cleaning and flushing, encapsulation, solidification,

stabilization, electro kinetics, vitrification, and vapour extraction) are costly and do not make the soil appropriate for plant development. On the other hand, biological techniques (bioremediation) promote the growth of plants on contaminated soils. Because it is accomplished by natural processes, it is an environmentally beneficial strategy. When compared to other cleanup procedures, bioremediation is also a more affordable option [2].

II. HEAVY METAL CONTAMINATION

Elements with metallic characteristics including ductility, malleability, conductivity, cation stability, and ligand selectivity are known as heavy metals. They are distinguished by a high relative atomic weight and relatively high density with an atomic number larger than 20. Some heavy metals, including Co, Cu, Fe, Mn, Mo, Ni, V, and Zn, are needed by life in very small amounts. However, these substances can become toxic to organisms in large

quantities. Other heavy metals like Pb, Cd, Hg, and As (a metalloid but commonly referred to as a heavy metal) are exceedingly damaging to both plants and animals and are thus considered to be the "primary risks" because they have no good effects on organisms [3].

Heavy metals may alter soil characteristics, particularly biological characteristics. In comparison to monitoring soil physical and chemical characteristics, monitoring changes in soil microbiological and biochemical properties after contamination may be used to assess the level of soil pollution. This is because these approaches are more sensitive and produce findings more quickly. The quantity, variety, and activity of soil microorganisms are impacted by heavy metals. Numerous variables, including soil temperature, pH, clay minerals, organic matter, inorganic anions and cations, and the chemical forms of the metal, affect how poisonous certain metals are to microorganisms [7].

III. EFFECT OF HEAVY METAL POLLUTED SOIL ON PLANT GROWTH

The heavy metals that are easily soluble by root exudates or present as soluble components in soil solution are those that are accessible for plant absorption. Even while some heavy metals are necessary for the growth and maintenance of plants, too much of these metals can be hazardous to them. Plants can collect additional non-essential metals because they can do the same with essential metals. Metals cannot be broken down, thus when concentrations inside the plant surpass ideal levels, they have a negative direct and indirect impact on the plant [4].

High metal concentrations have several direct harmful consequences, such as cytoplasmic enzyme inhibition and oxidative stress-related cell structural destruction. Furthermore, the detrimental effects that heavy metals have on the development and functioning of soil microbes may potentially indirectly have an impact on plant growth. Due to interference by heavy metals with the actions of soil microorganisms, plant metabolism-related enzyme activities may also be hindered. Depending on the specific heavy metal used in the process, different heavy metals have different effects on plant development [6].

IV. BIOREMEDIATION OF HEAVY METAL POLLUTED SOILS

Utilizing living things (plants, bacteria, etc.) to clean up contaminated soil is known as bioremediation. Due to the perception that it results from natural processes, this type of soil remediation is widely accepted. It is a way of soil remediation that is similarly economical. During bioremediation, heavy metals can only be changed from one organic complex or oxidation state to another; they cannot be broken down. Heavy metals can alter in oxidation state to become less poisonous, more readily volatilized, more water soluble (allowing for leaching removal), less water soluble (allowing for precipitation and easy removal from the environment), or less bioavailable. Bioremediation

of heavy metals can be achieved via the use of microorganisms, plants, or the combination of both organisms [5].

V. USING PLANTS FOR REMEDIATION OF HEAVY METAL POLLUTED SOILS

A component of bioremediation known as phytoremediation employs plants to clean contaminated soils. It is useful when the contaminants are dispersed over a large region and when they are near the plant's roots. Different strategies can be used to achieve phytoremediation of soils contaminated with heavy metals. Phyto stabilization, Phytoextraction, and Phytovolatilization are some of these methods.

VI. PHYTOEXTRACTION

The most typical type of phytoremediation is this one. It includes the buildup of heavy metals in the phytoremediation plants' roots and shoots. Later, these plants are collected and burned. The following traits are typically present in plants that are utilized for phytoextraction: quick growth rate, large biomass, extensive root system, and capacity to withstand high concentrations of heavy metals. These plants' capacity to withstand large concentrations of heavy metals may cause metal buildup in the section that may be harvested, which could be problematic due to food chain contamination [12].

Hyperaccumulators are ideal for phytoremediation since they collect 10 to 500 times more metals than regular plants. The ability of these plants to withstand rising metal concentrations is a crucial trait that makes hyperaccumulation conceivable (hyper tolerance). This may be due to the metals being excluded from the plants or the compartmentalization of these metal ions, which prevents the metals from reaching the cellular sites necessary for vital processes like respiration and cell division. The metals may be retained in the vacuolar compartments or cell walls [8].

The below table consist of various plants used in phytoextraction of heavy metals by hyperaccumulation.

FAMILY	SPECIES	HEAVY METALS
Asteraceae	<i>Berkheya coddii</i>	Ni
Asteraceae	<i>Helianthus annuus</i>	Pb, Cd, Zn
Brassicaceae	<i>Alyssum bertolonii</i>	Ni
Brassicaceae	<i>Alyssum murale</i>	Ni
Brassicaceae	<i>Arabidopsis halleri</i>	Zn, Cd
Caryophyllaceae	<i>Minuartia verna</i>	Zn, Cd, Pb
Crassulaceae	<i>Sedum alfredi</i>	Pb
Euphorbiaceae	<i>Euphorbia cheiradenia</i>	Cu, Fe, Pb, Zn
Fabaceae	<i>Astragalus racemosus</i>	Se
Fabaceae	<i>Medicago sativa</i>	Pb
Poaceae	<i>Spartina argentinensis</i>	Cr
Pteridaceae	<i>Pteris vittata</i>	As
Pteridaceae	<i>Pteris vittata</i>	Hg
Violaceae	<i>Viola boashanensis</i>	Pb, Zn, Cd

VII. PHYTOSTABILIZATION

Metals can be immobilized by plants, which lowers their bioavailability by preventing leaching and erosion. When phytoextraction is neither desired nor even feasible, it is typically utilized. Precipitation, sorption, metal valence reduction, or complexation

The following traits should be present in plants used for Phyto stabilization: a deep root system, the capacity to withstand soil conditions, ease of establishment and maintenance in the field, quick growth to give appropriate ground covering, longevity, and the capacity for self-propagation. The

Technology	Action on Contaminants	Main Type of Contaminants
Phyto stabilization	Retained in <u>situ</u>	Organics and metals
Phytovolatilization	Removed	Organics and metals
Phytoextraction	Removed	Metals

Comparison between phytoremediation technologies

all lead to the Phyto stabilization of heavy metals. Depending on the plant and soil amendment utilized, Phyto stabilization might be more or less effective. Through their root systems, plants contribute to soil stabilization and hence reduce soil erosion. Root systems of plants also stop leaching by reducing the amount of water that percolates through the soil. Additionally, plants provide surfaces for metal precipitation and sorption as well as protection from direct contact with contaminants for humans. It is crucial that the right plants are chosen for the Phyto stabilization of heavy metals based on the considerations [15].

application of soil amendments in Phyto stabilization aids in the inactivation of heavy metals, preventing plant absorption of metal and lowering biological activity. Most soil amendments employed in Phyto stabilization are organic components [16].

VIII. PHYTOVOLATILIZATION

In this type of phytoremediation, contaminants from the soil are taken up by plants, converted into volatile forms, and then transpired into the atmosphere. Most often, phytovolatilization is employed to clean up Hg-polluted soils. Mercuric ion, which is mercury's poisonous form, is changed

into a less dangerous form (elemental Hg). The issue with this process is that the new product created, elemental Hg, may be recycled by precipitation and

IX. PLANT MECHANISMS FOR METAL DETOXIFICATION

At toxic concentrations, heavy metals interfere with normal plant function and block metabolic processes in several ways, such as by displacing amino acids that are produced by the formation of bonds between heavy metals and sulfhydryl groups. The normal operation of enzymes and pigments in the disrupted biomolecules is hampered by metal toxicity, which interferes with the structure of the cytoplasmic membrane and consistently suppresses photosynthesis, respiration, and enzymatic activities. Redox-active metals (Cr, Cu, Mn, and Fe) and non-redox-active metals (Cd, Ni, Hg, Zn, and Al) can be classified according to their physio-chemical characteristics [8].

In plants, redox active metals create oxidative stress that directly disrupts cell homeostasis, alters DNA structure and function, damages the chloroplast and accessory pigments, and ultimately results in the destruction of the cell by ROS. Alternately, non-redox active metals can indirectly cause oxidative stress through a variety of methods that suppress antioxidative enzymes or activate ROS-producing enzymes [9].

Plants naturally have active antioxidant systems that eliminate the toxicity caused by ROS. Physical barriers like thick cuticles, biologically active tissues like trichomes and cell walls, and mycorrhizal symbiosis can act as biophysical barriers when plants are stressed by heavy metals. These are the first lines of defense against heavy metals in plants. The plant launches a number of cellular defense mechanisms to stop and lessen the harmful effects of the heavy metal if these metal ions get past these barriers and enter tissues and cells.

By producing both enzyme-based and non-enzymatic antioxidants that neutralize free radicals including ascorbate, glutathione, alkaloids, tocopherols, and superoxide dismutase, catalase, and glutathione reductase, plant cells minimize the harmful effects of free radicals. The production of phytochelatin synthase, an enzyme that readily binds

then redeposited into lakes and rivers, which again repeats the process of anaerobic bacteria producing methyl-Hg [15].

to heavy metals at lethal levels, the production of metallothioneins, and the production of proline are all defense mechanisms used by plants. Proline serves as a compatible and metabolic osmolyte, a component of cell walls, a free radical scavenger, an antioxidant, and a macromolecule stabilizer [14].

The enzyme phytochelatin synthase creates phytochelatins (PCs), which are short-chain thiol-rich repetitions of low-molecular weight peptides that protect plants from environmental stresses like salinity, drought, herbicides, and heavy metals. They are employed as biomarkers to identify heavy metal stress in plants at an early stage. Plant metallothioneins (MTs) are low-molecular-weight, metal-binding proteins with a high cysteine content that are produced as a result of mRNA translation. They show high affinity for a variety of metals, including Cu, Zn, Cd, and As, through cellular sequestration, intracellular metal ion homeostasis, and modification of metal transport. Along with helping to detoxify heavy metals, plant MTs also help to maintain the redox balance, repair damaged DNA, promote cell growth and proliferation, and scavenge ROS. Under various climatic conditions, mutualistic symbiotic associations between Arbuscular mycorrhizal and the roots of most vascular plant species also take place. In these associations, the arbuscular mycorrhizal organisms benefit from the photosynthetic assimilations provided by the plants and help to improve the position of the plants' mineral nutrition and their tolerance to abiotic stresses and pollutants [9].

X. INCREASING BIOAVAILABILITY OF HEAVY METALS

Beyond plant selection and performance, boosting heavy metal bioavailability is a crucial tactic for enhancing phytoextraction's effectiveness. There are times when the heavy metals in the soil are not easily accessible for bioaccumulation. Only a small part of the overall number of heavy metals in the soil are soluble and available for plant uptake. In comparison to other heavy metals, Zn and Cd are more bioavailable to plants. Heavy metals and

metalloids can be divided into three categories based on their bioavailability in soil: least bioavailable (Pb, Cr), moderately bioavailable (Co, Mn), and readily bioavailable (Cd, Ni, Zn, As, Se, Cu) [7].

[12] The capacity of some heavy metals, like Pb, to be absorbed from soil is severely hampered by their low bioavailability, which lowers the efficiency of phytoextraction. The inherent solubility of heavy metals, the characteristics of the soil, and their binding to soil particles all affect how bioavailable they are in the soil. There are a number of soil physicochemical characteristics that can affect the bioavailability and solubility of heavy metals in the soil, including the presence of chelating agents, the soil pH, and microbial activity.

[13] Different tactics can be used by a plant itself to increase the bioavailability of heavy metals. The concentration of heavy metals in the soil rises as a result of root exudates acidifying the rhizosphere by decreasing soil pH, which encourages the desorption of heavy metals from insoluble complexes to generate free ions. Additionally, plants can secrete substances that increase the solubility, mobility, and bioavailability of heavy metals in the soil in the rhizosphere, such as phytosiderophores, carboxylates, and organic acids. These substances influence the physicochemical characteristics of the soil and facilitate heavy metal chelation.

XI. PYROLYSIS

[11] The term "pyrolysis" refers to the chemical degradation of organic compounds brought about by heat in the absence of oxygen. Since true pyrolytic systems work with fewer than stoichiometric amounts of oxygen, it is not practical to create an environment that is entirely devoid of oxygen. Any pyrolytic system will include some oxygen, hence minimal oxidation will take place. Thermal desorption will also take place if there are any volatile or semi volatile compounds in the trash. Hazardous organic compounds are converted by pyrolysis into gaseous elements, trace amounts of liquid, and a solid residue (coke) that contains fixed carbon and ash. Combustible gases, such as carbon monoxide, hydrogen, and methane, as well as other hydrocarbons, are produced during the pyrolysis of organic materials. Cooling the off gases causes liquids to condense, leaving behind an oil/tar deposit

and tainted water. The standard conditions for pyrolysis include pressure and operating temperatures of more than 430 °C (800 °F). Further processing of the pyrolysis gases is necessary. The off gases might be flared, partially condensed, and treated in a secondary combustion chamber. Additionally needed is particle removal machinery like wet scrubbers or fabric filters.

One of the worst environmental catastrophes in human history was unintentionally brought about by a team of engineers working on the Chernobyl Nuclear Power Plant's No. 4 Reactor on April 26, 1986, near the Ukrainian city of Pripyat. Hundreds of lives were lost as 50 tons of radioactive material were spilled into the environment. Pripyat was abandoned as a radioactive wasteland after being evacuated [12].

Helianthus annuus, a common sunflower, is a hyperaccumulator of harmful heavy metals. Sunflowers take metal compounds from the soil's depths and transfer them to the stem, leaves, and flower head, just like many other hyperaccumulating plants do. Hyperaccumulating plants are employed in a procedure known as phytoremediation to remove environmental contaminants [11].

Particularly skilled at removing radioactive elements, such as the cesium-137 and strontium-90 discovered at Chernobyl, are sunflowers. Sunflower fields were established following the Chernobyl tragedy to collect these radioactive elements from the soil. Once the sunflowers had fully matured, they were collected and securely disposed of using pyrolysis. The radioactive metals are left behind while all the organic carbon in the plant is burned up during this process. Then, these metals are vitrified into Pyrex glass and kept underground in a protected container. Hence pyrolysis comes in handy to produce this glass and store it.

XII. METHODOLOGY

PREPARATION OF BIOMASS:

The biomass was gathered from a location used for phytoremediation. The biomass was carefully divided into small pieces, cleaned with deionized water, and baked for 72 hours at 60 °C. A high-speed rotary cutterbar was used to grind the dried biomass into particles around 1 mm in size,

which were then placed in a drying jar for experimentation [10].

ADSORPTION EXPERIMENT:

The adsorption tests were conducted in 250 mL conical flasks containing biomass at a temperature of around 20 °C and oscillating at a rate of 180 rpm. Infected water with Cd and Cu concentrations of 1.43 and 1.29 mmol/L was stimulated using an acetate Cd and Cu solution. By adding 1.0 mol/L of both HCL and NaOH, the starting solution's pH was changed to 2.0, 4.0, and 6.0. 3 g of biomass were combined with 150 mL of acetate Cd and Cu solutions in 250 mL conical flasks at intervals ranging from 10 to 180 minutes for the adsorption experiment. Following sorption, the suspension liquid underwent filtering to separate the components, and the concentration of heavy metals in the filtrate was calculated [14].

PYROLYSIS EXPERIMENT:

First, a thermal gravimetric analyzer was used with biomass. A 20 mg of biomass was deposited in the burning chamber and heated at a rate of 10°C/min from ambient temperature (25 °C) to 950 °C before being pyrolyzed. To regulate the oxygen level, a high-quality nitrogen stream was continually injected into the burning chamber at a flow rate of 40 mL/min [11].

A laboratory-scale pyrolysis experiment in a tube furnace should be planned based on the ideal pyrolysis temperature for the biomass. The inner diameter of the quartz tube in the tube furnace was 130 mm, and its length was 1 m. The 1.5 g sample of adsorbent biomass was dragged towards the center of the heating zone in a porcelain boat, and a quartz tube was heated by an electric ring to temperatures of 450 and 950 °C for 2 hours at a rate of 10 °C/min. The quartz tube was continually purged with nitrogen at 0.5 L/min to remove the associated gases, and the liquid waste was collected in bottles that were cooled with absorption liquid. Nitric acid and perchloric acid were used to digest the products of pyrolysis and biomass.

XIII. CONCLUSION

Due to modifications in their physiological and biochemical activity, plants living in heavy metal-polluted soils exhibit decreased growth. This

is especially true when the heavy metal in question has no positive effects on plant growth and development. Heavy metal-polluted soil can be efficiently treated via bioremediation. Since it is a nondisruptive type of soil remediation, it is most suitable when the remedied site is employed for crop production. Phytoremediation, or the use of plants instead of microbes, is a more popular method of bioremediating heavy metals. Different processes are used by plants to clean up heavy metal-contaminated soil. The most popular method of phytoremediation used to remediate heavy metal-polluted soils is phytoextraction. It guarantees that the contaminant is completely removed. The effectiveness of bioremediation is increased when microbes and plants are used together. Numerous phytoremediation programmes have successfully included both mycorrhizal fungus and other PGPR. The kind of microbes and plants used, as well as the amount of the heavy metal in the soil, all have a role in how well this combination of organisms works.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Gallego, José Luis R., et al. "Effective bioremediation of soil from the Burgan oil field (Kuwait) using compost: A comprehensive hydrocarbon and DNA fingerprinting study." *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety* 247: 114267.
- [2]. Prabakaran, S., et al. "A state-of-the-art review on the environmental benefits and prospects of Azolla in biofuel, bioremediation and biofertilizer applications." *Industrial Crops and Products* 183:114942.
- [3]. Lin, Zhong, et al. "Effects of biochar pyrolysis temperature on di-2-ethylhexyl phthalate (DEHP) removal performance and microbial community structure in coastal sediments." *Environmental Technology & Innovation* 24 (221): 102004.
- [4]. Li, Xiao, Yufeng Wu, and Zhe Tan. "An overview on bioremediation technologies for soil pollution in E-waste dismantling areas." *Journal of Environmental Chemical Engineering* (2022): 107839.
- [5]. Liang, Rui-Ze, et al. "Multi-index assessment of heavy metal contamination in surface sediments of the Pearl River estuary intertidal zone." *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 186 : 114445.

- [6]. Kumar, Vivek Vijaya, et al. "Heavy metal contamination, distribution and source apportionment in the sediments from Kavvayi Estuary, South-west coast of India." *Total Environment Research Themes* 3: 100019.
- [7]. Mohajane, Chaka, and Munyaradzi Manjoro. "Sediment-associated heavy metal contamination and potential ecological risk along an urban river in South Africa." *Heliyon*: e12499.
- [8]. Kuzyakov, Yakov, and Alexei Raskatov. "Effect of heavy metals contamination on root-derived and organic matter-derived CO₂ efflux from soil planted with *Zea mays*." *European Journal of Soil Biology* 44.5-6: 501-508.
- [9]. Kafel, A., et al. "Effect of heavy metal contamination on host plants and aphids. Detoxification capabilities of organisms." *Comparative Biochemistry and Physiology, Part A* 1.151 : S49.
- [10]. Golia, Evangelia E. "The impact of heavy metal contamination on soil quality and plant nutrition. Sustainable management of moderate contaminated agricultural and urban soils, using low cost materials and promoting circular economy." *Sustainable Chemistry and Pharmacy* 33: 101046.
- [11]. Wang, Chenguang, et al. "Study on secondary oxidation characteristics of coal gangue at different pyrolysis rank." *Fuel* 345: 128231.
- [12]. Iyyappan, J., et al. "Promising strategies of circular bioeconomy using heavy metal phyto-remediated plants—A critical review." *Chemosphere* : 137097.
- [13]. Kaur, Sukhchain, et al. "Bioremediation: A favorable perspective to eliminate heavy metals from polluted soil." *Metagenomics to Bioremediation*. Academic Press,. 209-230.
- [14]. da Silva, Nickolas Menezes, et al. "Genome sequencing of *Cladophialophora exuberans*, a novel candidate for bioremediation of hydrocarbon and heavy metal polluted habitats." *Fungal Biology*.
- [15]. Praveen, R., and R. Nagalakshmi. "Review on bioremediation and phyto-remediation techniques of heavy metals in contaminated soil from dump site." *Materials Today: Proceedings*.
- [16]. Okoroafor, Precious Uchenna, et al. "Phytoextraction of rare earth elements, germanium and other trace elements as affected by fertilization and liming." *Environmental Technology & Innovation* 28: 102607.